

Volume 9, Number 2, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

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**LAND SUITABILITY ASSESSMENT FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT USING GIS AND
MULTI-CRITERIA EVALUATION APPROACH IN KATSINA METROPOLIS,
KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA**

Yahaya Zayyana Ibrahim

Department of Environmental Management, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina
Department of Meteorology and Climate Change Science, African Aviation and Aerospace
University, Abuja
yahaya.zayyana@umyu.edu.ng

&

Safiyanu Mohammed

Department of Geography, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina
muhammedsufiyanu7@gmail.com

Abstract: *The study assessed land suitability for urban development in Katsina Metropolis, Katsina State Nigeria. As a city with rapid urban development, there is a need to understand the pattern and the direction of development. Thus, the study aimed to ascertain the nature of land use changes in the area. Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) data with 30 meters spatial resolution and sentinel-2 Satellite image were used to produce the slope, aspect and drainage map of the study area. Sentinel-2 imagery was used to generate the land use and land cover through supervised image classification. A Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE) using pair wise comparison in Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to weigh the factors influencing site suitability for urban development. A weighted overlay in Arc GIS was used to produce the site suitability map. The study revealed that crop land occupied the highest land cover with 57.793% (77.57km²), build up area was next occupying about 25.86% (34.72km²) of the area. Vegetation occupied 9.36% (12.57 km²), bare surface accounted for 6.56% (8.81km²), while water bodies was least with 0.43% (21.5sq. km). The study also revealed that 36.56 sq.km (27.65%) of the land fell under very low suitable sites for urban development, 26.29 sq. km (19.88%) was found to be low suitable sites, 21.32 sq. km (16.13%) of the total area was moderately suitable, while 23.71 sq. km (17.93%) of the area was highly suitable and 24.33 sq. km (18.41%) was very highly suitable site. The study recommended that the Northwest, Northeast and some portion of South Western parts of Katsina Metropolis should be considered as suitable areas for new urban development.*

Key Words: Land Suitability, GIS, SRTM, Urban Development, Land Use

INTRODUCTION

Land suitability refers to the ability of a particular type of land to support a specific use, and the

process of land suitability classification involves the evaluation and grouping of particular land areas in terms of their suitability for a defined use (Prakash, 2003). Land suitability analysis is thus

concerned with evaluation of the fitness of a given tract of land for a defined use (Steiner et al., 2000). In other words, it is the process to determining whether the land resource is suitable for some specific uses. It is also undertaken to determine the suitability level. In order to determine the most desirable direction for future development, the suitability for various land uses should be carefully examined with the aim of directing growth to the most appropriate sites. Establishing appropriate suitability factors is the construction of suitability analysis.

Historically, suitability analysis was developed as a method for planners to connect spatially independent factors within the environment and, consequently to provide a more unitary view of their interactions. Suitability analysis techniques integrate three factors of an area: location, development activities, and biophysical/environmental processes (Miller, et al, 1998). Land use suitability analysis aims at identifying the most appropriate spatial pattern for future land uses according to specific requirements, preferences, or predictors of some activity (Collins et al., 2001).

Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) technologies have great potential for acquisition of detailed and accurate land use information for management and planning of urban regions. However, the determination of land use data with high geometric and thematic accuracy is generally limited (Herold et al., 2002). Planned settlement can be defined as habitable living environment for the people. It provides comfortable dwelling conditions, efficient infrastructure, social- wellbeing, and improved living standards and quality of life for inhabitants in the area. Unfortunately, the reality is often quite different. Haphazard and uncontrolled settlement expansion is the rule.

Cities with rapid urban growth are characterized by pressing need of many housing

dwelling, needs for more land spaces and other urban services and facilities, which in most cases are inadequate (Bhatta, 2009). As results of this uncontrolled and therefore, unpredictable demand, issues like shortage of housing, insufficient infrastructure and services, unplanned physical development, illegal settlements are common in most of the urban centers. In developing countries, planning of housing and road locations are mainly evaluated based on factors such as socio-economic, political, land use policies and related infrastructure conditions. Therefore, unexpected problems are frequently encountered during the implementation, which often add to the cost of construction and construction failures. (Kevin and Hack, 1995).

A number of problems are attributed to the unplanned settlement, this includes housing development in inappropriate locations, loss of agricultural lands, reduction of amount and quality of water bodies and land degradation among others. For example, permanent houses are being built up in drainage valleys, which is causing severe storm water drainage problems and flooding during the rainy season. This pattern of settlement development will not only increase the cost of construction and maintenance of infrastructure in the area, but also greatly affects the environment. Therefore, by considering the physical problem prevailing in the area, the research intended to look at problems relating to housing and local roads construction in terms of soil, drainage density, slope and aspect road network, and site conditions. Many researches have been carried out on land suitability for development. For example, Kumar and Biswas (2014) analyzed the site suitability for urban development of a hill town using GIS based multi-criteria evaluation technique in Nahan Town, Himachal Pradesh, India. Factors considered include: slope, road proximity, land use, land values, soil and geomorphological

factors. The data used was Cartosat-1 and LISS-IV and six thematic information layers were analyzed in ArcGIS 9.3 software to identify suitable areas in Nahan town. The study used GIS based Overlay Weight age Average (OWA) Sum and Weighted Linear Combination (WLC). The undulating terrain, steep slope, varied soil depth and high building cost give the impression to find out suitable sites for urban development in the Nahan Town. Six factors (slope, road proximity, land use, land values, soil and geomorphology) were identified for criteria evaluation. They showed that 0.1157km² fell under very low suitable, 1.6835km² under low suitable, 1.2090km² under moderately suitable, 0.3663km² under high suitable and 0.1248 km² under very high suitable. The result further revealed that highly suitable areas for urban development is either agricultural or forest type. The resultant suitability map indicates primary suitable lands for future urban growth are located adjacent to the established urban areas.

From the aforementioned works and other literature reviewed, this study was conceived

to assess the physical land suitability for urban development in Katsina metropolis using Remote Sensing, GIS and Multi-criteria evaluation approach.

METHODOLOGY

RECONNAISSANCE SURVEY:

A reconnaissance survey was conducted by the researchers in order to get acquainted with the study area. During the survey, observations were made on the type of land cover (prominent features such as building, roundabout, institutions etc.) available in the study area and their coordinates were taken with aid of the Global Position System (GPS) in order to guide the researchers for the analysis.

TYPE AND SOURCES OF DATA USED:

Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. Primary data that were used are satellite imageries Sentinel-2, Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM, Road network (Table 1). Secondary data were sourced from newspapers, journals, textbooks etc.

Table 1: Types and Sources of Data

S/No	Type of Data	Spatial Resolution	Date	Source	Purpose
1.	Sentinel -2	10 meters Resolution	2020	United State Geological Survey Website (USGS)	Land use/land cover analysis
2	SRTM (DEM)	30 meters Resolution	2013	United State Geological Survey Website (USGS)	Slope, drainage density and aspect
3	Road network	-	2019	Grid 3 Nigeria (https://grid3.gov.ng/)	Road distance

Source: Authors Compilation, 2023

DATA PROCESSING:

- i **IMAGE PROCESSING:** Satellite imagery of Katsina Metropolis was enhanced to improve visualization of features using the SCP tool in QGIS. The imagery was assigned (Universal Traverse Mercator) coordinate using QGIS. The UTM system was adopted because of its high reliability since its measurements are cited in linear and decimal units rather than in angular and non-decimal units.
- ii **GENERATION OF LAND USE MAP:** The Sentinel-2 image of Katsina Metropolis (10m) was projected using the Universal Traverse Mercator (UTM) Zone 32 North with datum WGS 1984. The area of interest was clipped out of the imagery. Finally, the SCP tool in QGIS was used to carry out supervised classification using a maximum likelihood algorithm with five classes (water body, vegetation, farmland, bare land and built-up area).
- iii **GENERATION OF SLOPE AND ASPECT MAPS:** The digital elevation model (DEM) Module creation of Arc GIS10.3 was used to create slope and aspect of Katsina Metropolis from Digital Elevation Dataset of Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM). This was used to produce a slope and aspect map of the study area using spatial analysis tools in Arc GIS 10.3.
- iv **GENERATION OF DRAINAGE DENSITY:** The drainage density of Katsina metropolis was generated from

shuttle radar topography mission data. The area of interest was clipped out of Shuttle radar topography. The spatial analysis tool in Arc GIS software was used in computing the drainage density of the area.

STEPS USED IN DERIVING CRITERION WEIGHT USING AHP:

The relationship between the six causative thematic maps and their attributes were derived using the analytic hierarchy process (AHP). The methodology used for deriving their weights involved the following steps:

STEP 1: Defining the problem clearly and decomposing it into various thematic layers containing different features/classes of the individual themes so that they form a network of the model (Saaty, 1980).

STEP 2: Generating Pair-wise comparison matrices: The relative important values were determined with Saaty's 1-9 scale. where a score of 1 represents equal importance between the two attributes, and a score of 9 indicates the extreme importance of an attribute compared to the other one (Saaty, 1980).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TYPES OF EXISTING LAND USE LAND COVER IN THE AREA

Supervised image classification was used to classify the 2020 Sentinel-2 image into bare land, vegetation, crop land, and built-up land and water bodies. The area coverage of the land use in the study is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Area coverage of existing land use in Katsina metropolis in 2020

S/No	LULC	Area (Km ²)	Percentage
1	Built-up Area	34.72	25.86%
2	Bareland	8.81	6.56%
3	Cropland	77.57	57.79%
4	Vegetation	12.57	9.36%
5	Water Bodies	0.58	0.43%
		134.24	100.00%

Source: Authors Analysis, 2023.

The study revealed that built-up covered an area of 34.72km², which accounted for (25.86%), while bare land had 8.81km² and accounted for (6.56%), and cropland had a 77.57km² area, which accounted for (57.79%). Vegetation covered 12.57km² and accounted

for (9.36%) and water bodies covered 0.58km², which accounted for (0.43%) respectively. In summary, cropland has the highest coverage with (57.79%), while water bodies have the least coverage with (0.43%).

Figure 1: Land use and land cover of Katsina metropolis (2020)

Source: Authors Analysis, 2023

The spatial distribution of the LULC in Katsina metropolis as at year 2020 is shown in Figure 1 . From the south and southwest parts of the study area, a large portion of the built-up area were found, indicated in red. While smaller portions of bare land were found in the northwest and southeast, which is indicated by the yellow colour. Also, a larger portion of croplands is indicated in purple, were located

in the northern part and southeast. Vegetation, which is indicated by the green color, was mostly located at the center of the study area and a smaller amount in the western part. Water bodies that could hardly be located are blue in color, a very small portion of which was located at the center of the study area.

FACTORS INFLUENCING LAND SUITABILITY FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT

This study examined and adopted the five criteria used by Kumar and Biswas (2014) to determine site suitability for urban development in the region. These factors include accessibility, network, slope, aspect, drainage density, and land cover of the area. A pairwise comparison was used for each

factor using the Analytical Hierarchical process (AHP) to assign the weightages.

SLOPE:

The slope map was derived from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) generated from Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission 30m spatial resolution in ArcGIS 10.3 using the spatial analysis - toolbox. Figure 2 showed the slope map of the study.

Figure 2: Slope of Katsina Metropolis
 Source: Authors Analysis, 2023

Table 3: Reclassification of Slope according to the order of suitability

S/No	Slope	Area	Percentage	Suitability	Weightage
1	< - 5	127.46	96.29%	Very High	0.50
2	5 - 10	4.90	3.70%	High	0.33
3	10 - >	0.02	0.01%	Moderate	0.17
		132.38	100.00%		

The suitability of slope in the study area is shown in Table 3, with areas less than five degrees occupying 127.46km², which accounted for (96.29%) and is considered to be very highly suitable. While the slope ranging from five to ten degrees occupies 4.90km², and accounted for (3.70%), which was also high and considered to be suitable. Areas with greater than ten degrees in the study area occupied 0.02km² and accounted for (0.01%) of the total area, which was still considered moderately suitable for urban development.

In summary, the study area's slope was considered to be suitable for urban development. The slope less than five degrees has the highest percentage (96.29%), while the slope greater than ten degrees had the lowest percentage (0.01%).

SUITABLE SITES FOR NEW URBAN DEVELOPMENT IN THE STUDY AREA

Application of suitability analysis is a procedure that includes the use of criterion

maps in conjunction with defined criteria weights, as well as the submission of these data to different processing modules in Arc GIS, in order to produce a ranked suitability map.

To identify the most appropriate locations for future urban development in Katsina metropolis, all the thematic maps of the factors influencing urban development in the region were weighted and structured according to Kumar and Biswas (2014). The weights of the factors influencing urban development within the study area is presented in Table 4.

Pairwise comparison matrix and weights of factors using AHP shown in Table 4, indicated that slope was weighted the highest (0.5), followed by proximity to roads (0.26), land use and land cover (0.13), and drainage density (0.12). (0.07). the least contributor to urban development in the study area is the aspect which was weighed (0.04).

Table 4: Pairwise comparison matrix and weights of factors influencing urban development

Criteria	Slope	Road Proximity	Land Cover	Drainage Density	Aspect	Weights
Slope	1	3	4	8	9	0.50
Road proximity	0.33	1	3	4	8	0.26
Land use/cover	0.25	0.33	1	3	4	0.13
Drainage Density	0.12	0.25	0.33	1	3	0.07
Aspect	0.11	0.12	0.25	0.33	1	0.04

Consistency Ratio=0.04

With a consistency ratio (CR) of 0.04, the judgment was consistent and result accepted. With the help of the Arc GIS weighted sum toolbox, the integration of five (5) effective criteria (factors) was completed in order to create a land suitable for urban development.

The appropriate locations were categorized as follows: not suitable (red), low suitable (orange), moderate suitable (yellow), high suitable (light green), and very high suitable (green) respectively.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of suitable areas for urban development
Source: Authors Analysis, 2023

Table 5: Area Coverage of Suitable areas for Urban Development

S/No	Suitability	Area (km ²)	Percentage
1	Non-Suitable	36.56	27.65%
2	Low Suitable	26.29	19.88%
3	Moderate Suitable	21.32	16.13%
4	High Suitable	23.71	17.93%
5	Very High Suitable	24.33	18.41%
		132.21	100.00%

Source: Authors Analysis, 2023

As presented in table 5 and figure 3, the study revealed that the non-suitable area, which is indicated in red, occupied 36.56km², and accounted for 27.65% of the total study area. This is located in the southern part and the center of the study area. Secondly, low-suitable areas are indicated as orange and occupied 26.29km², which accounted for

19.88% of the area, and these can be located in the north and northeast. Moderately suitable lands occupied 21.32km² and accounted for 16.13%, as shown in yellow, some of these can be found in the northwest and patches in the northeast and southeast respectively.

Finally, highly suitable areas that occupied 23km² and accounted for 17.93% of the area are located northwest, southeast, and northeast. The areas with very high suitability in the study area occupied 24.33km², which accounted for 18.41%. This is indicated in green and is located in the northwest, northeast, and some portions of the southwest.

CONCLUSION

This study applied weighed overlay multi-criteria method, implemented in GIS and assessed land suitability for urban development in Katsina metropolis, Katsina State Nigeria. Based on the researched literature, this assessment developed an index of the land suitability factors for land-use appropriateness. The study produced a suitability map of the area, indicating different portions of lands and their recommended suitable uses for urban development. Key findings of the study revealed that, slope less than five degrees occupied 127.46km² and accounted for (96.29%) was considered to be very highly suitable for urban development in the area. Additionally, slope ranging from five to ten degrees occupied 4.90km² and accounted for 3.70% is equally considered high and suitable for urban development. Finally, areas with the slope greater than ten degrees occupied 0.02km² and accounts for 0.01% is considered moderately suitable.

Proximity urban lands to road network also revealed that area with less than 100 meters distance occupied 20.20km² and accounted for 15.05%, was considered very suitable. While areas between 300 to 500 meters distance occupied 14.95km² and accounted for 11.13% was considered moderately suitable. Finally, areas between 700 meters and above are considered to have very low suitability and occupied 62.26km² and accounted for 46.38% respectively.

Therefore, this study concluded that multi-criteria evaluation method and GIS can be used to assess land suitability for urban development which will assist in urban planning and land use management of urban areas. The study recommended that northwest, northeast and some portions of southwest of Katsina Metropolis should be considered for any new urban development in the area.

REFERENCES

- Bhatta, B. (2009). Analysis of urban growth pattern using remote sensing and GIS: a case study of Kolkata, India. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 30(18), 4733-4746.
- Collins, M.G. Steiner. F. R. and Rushman. M.I. (2001): Land use suitability analysis in the United States: historical development and promising technological achievements, *Environmental Management* 28:611 -621.
- Herold, M. Concelelis, H. and Clarke, K.C (2002) *Computers Environmental Urban Systems*, 29:369-399. 1. Pp 26-39.
- Kevin, L. and Hack, G., (1995). *Site Planning*, the MIT Press Cambridge, Massachusetts, and London, England.
- Kumar, M. and Biswas, (2014). Identification of Potential Sites for Urban Development Using GIS Based Multi Criteria Evaluation Technique. A Case Study of Shimla Municipal Area, Shimla District, Himachal Pradesh, India. *Journal of Settlements and Spatial Planning*, vol. 4, no. 1. 45-51.
- Miller, W., Collins, W.M.G., Steiner, F.R., Cook, E. (1998). An approach for greenway suitability analysis. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 42 (2-4), 91-105.
- Prakash, T. N. (2003, December). *Land suitability analysis for agricultural crops: a fuzzy multicriteria decision making approach*. Kolkata, West Bengal: ITC.

Saaty, T.L. (1980). *The Analytic Hierarchy Process*. McGraw-Hill, New York, USA. pp.: 20-25. Altuzarra, A., J. Maria, M. Jimenez and M. Salvador. (2007). A Bayesian prioritization procedure for AHP-group decision making. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, 182: 367-382.

Steiner, F., McSherry, L., and Cohen, J. (2000). Land Suitability Analysis for the upper Gila River Watershed. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 50, 2000, pp: 199-214.